

**AN ETHNOBOTANICAL STUDY OF MEDICINAL PLANTS WITH
HEPATOPROTECTIVE EFFECTS IN THE SERANGPANJANG REGION, SUBANG,
WEST JAVA, INDONESIA**

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ABSTRACT

Liver is a vital organ that plays a major role in the elimination of xenobiotics from the body. Diseases that affect the liver become major health problems and challenge health-care professionals as well as the pharmaceutical industry. Since the conventional treatment of liver diseases is associated with a wide range of adverse effects, botanical agents are commonly used. This research aims to document and preserve the use of ethnomedicinal to treat liver disease by communities in the Serangpanjang Region, Subang, West Java, Indonesia. Fieldwork was carried out from November to December 2025 using direct interviews, questionnaires, and discussions. Plant species are identified based on standard taxonomic methods, flower morphological characteristics, and where possible, using samples for comparison, as well as consultation with experts and the literature. The plant types obtained were grouped into families according to the Cronquist classification system. Plant names were checked against the Plant List (www.plantlist.org) and the International Plant Name Index (www.ipni.org). This research reports that 30 plant species are commonly used by people in the Serangpanjang Region to treat liver disease. Among the various plant parts used, leaves (50.0%) are most frequently used in making medicines, followed by rhizomes (13.3%), fruit (13.3%), flowers, stem, and seed (respectively 6.7%) and rind (3.3%). Meanwhile, the most frequently used preparation methods were decoction (76.7%) and infusion (23.3%). The results of this research confirm that people in the Serang panjang Region still rely heavily on medicinal plants for their health care system, especially for the treatment of liver disease with the most frequently used parts of the leaves and their use in decoctions and infusions.

KEYWORDS: Traditional medicine, Ethnomedicinal plants, Serangpanjang Region, Liver disease.

INTRODUCTION

The liver is the primary body organ responsible for the metabolism of macronutrients and exogenous xenobiotic compounds among other functions.^[1] Impairment of liver function is harmful to health, and is responsible for a large number of deaths worldwide. Moreover, hepatic damage is a prominent cause of morbidity arising from the development of oxidative stress and lipid peroxidation after continuous exposure to liver toxins, from infection, excessive alcohol, consumption and

medications.^[2] One of the most common causes of liver disease is drug-induced liver damage, which presents a considerable clinical and regulatory challenge. Drug-induced hepatotoxicity manifests a wide range of symptoms, from asymptomatic elevation of liver enzymes to fulminant hepatic failure.^[3] Paracetamol (PCT) or acetaminophen is a clinically important over-the-counter drug, commonly used as an analgesic and antipyretic. Although, PCT is a safe drug at therapeutic doses, it may cause hepatic necrosis, nephrotoxicity,

hepatic lesions and ultimately death in overdose.^[4] PCT is activated and catalytically transformed by cytochrome P450 enzymes to the potentially dangerous metabolite N-acetyl-p-benzoquinoneimine (NAPQI/ NABQI), which initiates oxidative stress and glutathione depletion.^[5] Despite developments in modern medicine, there is a deficiency of reliable medications that protect the liver against harm and/or facilitate regeneration of hepatic cells. In this respect, active plant extracts have been employed to treat a variety of clinical conditions, including liver disease. As a consequence, the search for effective and safe medications to combat liver problems remains an ongoing quest.^[3] Medicinal plants have been widely used in traditional practices by different ethnic populations throughout the world for the prevention and/or treatment of several chronic diseases. Despite the development of newer technologies and advances in modern medicine, most of the world's population still relies on traditional systems of medicine to fulfill their medical care, especially in Indonesia.^[6] One of the Region in Indonesia that still uses herbal plants as an alternative treatment, especially to treat liver disease, is the Serangpanjang Region. This research aims to obtain detailed information about the use of herbal plants for alternative therapy for liver disease in Serangpanjang Region, Subang, West Java, Indonesia using a field survey method.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Serangpanjang is located in Subang Regency, West Java, Indonesia, with an area of 1,311,844 km². This area has an altitude of 1,000 meters above sea level with an average maximum air temperature of 31°C and a minimum of 21°C. Moreover, it is located between 06°41'49" South Latitude and 107°35'50" East Longitude. This region is a tropical climate area that is mostly inhabited by Sundanese tribes (90%) and other tribes (10%). Vegetation in the study area is in humid conditions with an average rainfall of 3,000 mm/year.

Data Collection

An extensive field survey was carried out to obtain information about medicinal plants from the Sundanese tribe in the study area. To document existing information about medicinal plants from tribal practitioners, several

field visits were conducted from November to December 2025 in the Serangpanjang Region, Subang, West Java, Indonesia. During the research, ethnomedicinal information was collected from middle-aged and older tribal practitioners in their local language (Sundanese), through direct interviews, questionnaires, and discussions. Information on local names of plants, plant parts used, preparation methods and administration routes (e.g., infusion, paste, juice and decoction) of all ethnomedicinal plants collected were recorded during the survey period.

Botanical Identification

Plant species are identified based on standard taxonomic methods, flower morphological characteristics, and where possible, using samples for comparison, as well as consultation with experts and the literature.^[7] The plant types obtained were grouped into families according to the Cronquist classification system, except for Pteridophyta and Gymnospermae.^[8] Plant names were checked against the Plant List (www.plantlist.org) and the International Plant Name Index (www.ipni.org).

Ethics Statement

All participants provided verbal consent before the interview and gave consent to publish the information they provided.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research revealed that 30 plant species are commonly used by local people to treat liver disease (Table 1). This shows that the study location is affordable in terms of biodiversity. Among the various plant parts used, leaves (50.0%) are most frequently used in making medicines, followed by rhizomes (13.3%), fruit (13.3%), flowers, stem, and seed (respectively 6.7%), and rind (3.3%). The use of leaves is reported to be easier to prepare and easier to extract active substances from them for treatment. At the same time, leaves have less effect on the mother plant.^[9] Meanwhile, the most frequently used preparation methods were decoction (76.7%) and infusion (23.3%). These results are in line with previous research which reported that the forms of traditional medicine most widely used by the community were decoctions and infusions.^[7]

Table 1: Ethnomedicinal plants, local name, part used, mode of administration, and dosage uses in Serangpanjang, Subang, West Java, Indonesia.

No	Species	Family	Local name	Parts used	Mode of administration	Dosage of use
1	<i>Adenanthera pavonine</i> L.	Fabaceae	Saga	Leaf	Decoction	10 grams once a day
2	<i>Allium sativum</i> L.	Alliaceae	Bawang Putih	Rhizome	Infusion	20 grams once a day
3	<i>Aloe vera</i> Burm.f.,	Asphodelaceae	Lidah Buaya	Stem	Decoction	100 grams once a day
4	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> Nees	Acanthaceae	Sambiloto	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day
5	<i>Annona muricata</i> L.	Annonaceae	Sirsak	Leaf	Infusion	200 grams once a

						day
6	<i>Averrhoa carambola</i> L.	Oxalidaceae	Belimbing	Leaf	Infusion	50 grams once a day
7	<i>Bauhinia variegata</i> L.	Fabaceae	Kachnar	Leaf	Decoction	15 grams once a day
8	<i>Cinnamomum verum</i> J.Presl	Lauraceae	Kayu Manis	Stem	Decoction	10 grams once a day
9	<i>Citrus aurantifolia</i> (Christm) Swingle	Rutaceae	Jeruk Nipis	Fruit	Decoction	20 grams once a day
10	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> L.	Fabaceae	Bunga Telang	Flower	Decoction	10 grams once a day
11	<i>Cosmos caudatus</i> Kunth	Asteraceae	Kenikir	Leaf	Decoction	30 grams once a day
12	<i>Curcuma longa</i> L.	Zingiberaceae	Kunyit	Rhizome	Infusion	50 grams once a day
13	<i>Garcinia mangostana</i> L.	Clusiaceae	Manggis	Rind	Infusion	50 grams once a day
14	<i>Hibiscus sabdariffa</i> L.	Malvaceae	Rosela	Flower	Decoction	80 grams once a day
15	<i>Kaempferia galanga</i> L.	Zingiberaceae	Kencur	Rhizome	Infusion	100 grams once a day
16	<i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	Anacardiaceae	Mangga	Leaf	Decoction	70 grams once a day
17	<i>Momordica charantia</i> L.	Cucurbitaceae	Pare	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day
18	<i>Morinda citrifolia</i> L.	Rubiaceae	Mengkudu	Fruit	Infusion	100 grams once a day
19	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lamk.	Moringaceae	Kelor	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day
20	<i>Nigella sativa</i> L.	Ranunculaceae	Jinten Hitam	Seed	Decoction	20 grams once a day
21	<i>Pandanus amaryllifolius</i> Roxb.	Pandanaceae	Pandan Wangi	Leaf	Decoction	10 grams once a day
22	<i>Persea americana</i> Mill.	Lauraceae	Alpukat	Seed	Decoction	30 grams once a day
23	<i>Phaleria macrocarpa</i> (Scheff.) Boerl	Thymelaceae	Mahkota Dewa	Fruit	Decoction	50 grams once a day
24	<i>Phyllanthus niruri</i> L.	Phyllanthaceae	Meniran	Leaf	Decoction	30 grams once a day
25	<i>Piper betle</i> L.	Piperaceae	Sirih	Leaf	Decoction	10 grams once a day
26	<i>Psidium guajava</i> L.	Myrtaceae	Jambu Biji	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day
27	<i>Solanum torvum</i> Sw.	Solanaceae	Tokakak	Fruit	Decoction	50 grams once a day
28	<i>Syzygium polyanthum</i> (Wight) Walpers	Myrtaceae	Salam	Leaf	Decoction	100 grams once a day
29	<i>Tinospora crispa</i> L.	Menispermaceae	Baratawali	Leaf	Decoction	70 grams once a day
30	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Rosc.	Zingiberaceae	Jahe	Rhizome	Decoction	100 grams once a day

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this research confirm that people in the Serangpanjang Region still rely heavily on medicinal plants for their health care system, especially for the treatment of liver disease with the most frequently used parts of the leaves and their use in decoctions and infusions.

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